

THE IMPACT OF NAIRA REDESIGN ON SMALL SCALE BUSINESSES IN BOSSO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, NIGER STATE: A STUDY OF THE 2022 REDESIGN PERIOD.

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Article Info

Keywords: Naira Redesign, Small-Scale Enterprises, Impact, Bosso Local Government Area, Monetary Policy.

DOI

10.5281/zenodo.19661628

Abstract

Currency redesign is not a novel concept and has been implemented in various countries throughout history. Its earliest instance dates back to ancient Greece, with more recent occurrences in countries such as Brazil, the United States, Botswana, and Turkey. In Nigeria, the most recent currency redesign took place in 2022. While the intent of this monetary policy was positive, it resulted in unintended consequences, particularly for small-scale businesses. Despite existing research on the broader impact of the Naira redesign on small-scale enterprises in Nigeria, there is a lack of a focused study on its effects in Bosso Local Government Area (LGA) of Niger State, a known hub for small businesses. This paper investigates the impact of the Naira redesign on small-scale businesses in Bosso LGA. Primary data were collected through oral interviews and online archives, while secondary sources included journal articles, newspapers, books, and theses. Findings indicate that the Naira redesign disrupted the flow of business capital, increased the cost of goods, and led to reduced sales and supply chain interruptions, thereby hampering economic and social development. The study recommends increased communication, better publicity and awareness, extended implementation periods, flexibility in policy enforcement, and greater collaboration with stakeholders to improve future currency redesign initiatives.

Introduction

The Justifying grounds for the redesign of currency vary from nation to nation. Various countries have resorted to redesigning and changing their currencies to promote economic steadiness, stabilize its economy, and combat

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disturbing issue such as counterfeiting, inflation, and currency hoarding. However, in an instance where these well-meaning monetary policies such as Naira Redesign affect the economic well-being of the populace, such policy effectiveness becomes a topic of heated debate.

According to The Guardian,² countries have redesigned their currencies for various reasons such as Inflation control (Brazil 1994), Economic Stabilization (Argentina 1992), Counterfeit Prevention (United States 1996). Others include Sweden which successfully transitioned to a cashless society in 2018 and Turkey which removed six zeros from the Lira in 2009.

In the African continent, countries such as Ghana (2007), Zimbabwe, South Africa (1961), Botswana (1976) and Nigeria has one way or the other changed their currencies³. Naira Redesign in Nigeria has a fascinating history. Redesigning bank denominations as a measure of currency management has been a long standing tradition in Nigeria's financial history since independence, and the 2022 Naira Redesign effort was a continuation of that practice.⁴ Hence the recent redesign was an extension of the monetary tradition.

The Naira was first introduced in Jan 1, 1973 replacing the Nigerian Pound at the rate of € 1 = ₦ 2. On 1st July 1959, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) came into full operation and they issued Nigeria's currency banknotes, this led to the withdrawal of banknotes and coins. In 1962, the currency was changed to reflect Nigeria's independence. In 2008, there were plans to redesign the Naira to combat counterfeiting and corruption.⁵ In 2022, the CBN Governor, Godwin Ifeanyi Emefiele, announced the redesigning of the Naira which was to be carried out from November 23rd, 2022 in which the ₦200, ₦500 and ₦1000 were redesigned and modified⁶. These new notes were launched and unveiled by President Muhammadu Buhari in the same month. This policy was intentioned to curb the high rate of currency forgery, inflation, money laundering and political manipulation as portrayed by economists but, most citizens especially the grassroots populace believe that the policy's execution was abrupt and detrimental to Small Scale businesses, and was possibly a diversion from the very main issues bedeviling the country at that time.

Small Scale Businesses or Enterprises are highly recognized as catalysts for economic growth in most economies. SMEs are highly regarded as the core in any economy as they perform a vital role in growth, employment creation, poverty reduction, innovative thinking and entrepreneurship.⁷ In Nigeria, Small Scale Enterprises are crucial to its economic development, one that absorbs a large chunk of its workforce. Adamu surmised that Small Scale businesses account for approximately 50% of the country's GDP (Gross Domestic Product) and 80% of employment opportunities.⁸ According to the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), SME's have been significant contributors' have been significant contributors to Nigeria's GDP as well; in 2017, they accounted for almost 48% of the total.⁹ In 2020, the NBS states that SMEs employ more than 84% of Nigeria's

² Guardian, the history of currency. Accessed at <https://editor.guardian.ng/opinion/the-history-ofcurrency-introduction-and-redesign-in-nigeria/2022>. Retrieved on 25 November 2024.

³ The Vanguard, the history of Currency Introduction and Redesign in Nigeria. Accessed at <https://vanguard.ng/opinion/the-2022>. Retrieved on 16 October 2024...

⁴ Central Bank of Nigeria "On Progress of Implementation of New Redesign Currency by the Central Bank of Nigeria" Press Statement by Godwin Emefiele, Jan 29, 2023, Accessed at <http://www.cbn.nig/en/>. Retrieved on April 14 2025.

⁵ Fasua. T. "Nigeria's Currency Redesign: A case study approach " Accessed at <https://www.premuimtimes interview.ng.com/ opinion/58038-nigerias-currency-redesign-2023-a case-study-approach-by-tope-fasua.html>, September 10 2023. Retrieved October 13 2024.

⁶ Pillah Tyodzer Patrick "Implementing Currency Redesign Policy of the Naira in Nigeria: Stratagems for Reaching Economic Steadiness" *Journal of Public Administration, Policy and Governance Research (JPAPGR)*, Vol.1 (1), (2023), 49-58.

⁷ Adeosun, O. T., & Shittu, A. I. "Small-medium enterprise formation and Nigerian economic growth" *Review of Economics and Political Science*. 7(4), 286-301(2021) Accessed at <https://doi.org/10.1108/REPS-07-2020-0089>. Retrieved on 9 July 2025.

⁸ Adamu A. Ibrahim, Moshood "Small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) and economic growth in Nigeria" *Journal of Management Research and Development (JMRD)*, Department of Business Administration, Nasarawa State University, Nasarawa State Nigeria 2 (1),(2011), 80- 98

⁹ National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) "National Accounts - Gross Domestic Product, 2017". (2018)Accessed at <https://nigerianstat.gov.ng/download/892>. Retrieved on 9 July 2025.

workers and comprise roughly 96% of all enterprises in the nation,¹⁰ and of recent in 2022, data released from the NBS shows that approximately 96% of Nigerian enterprises are SMEs, and they account for 50% of the country's GDP.¹¹

Having established the invaluableity of Small Businesses in Nigeria, it is quite pertinent to note that monetary policies adopted could adversely affect the thriving or collapse of these Small Scale Enterprises. One of such policies is Naira Redesign of 2022.

Bosso LGA (local government area) is home to numerous SSE's (Small Scale Enterprises) ranging from agricultural producers, traders, artisans, manufacturing industries, local bakeries, furniture making, small retail shops, petty trading, restaurants, artisanal crafts, Service providers and a host of others. The area has been a hub for small scale industries and commercial activities. Agreeable among intellectuals is the fact that Naira Redesign had an impact on the nation's economy especially on small businesses. It is therefore against this backdrop that the paper seeks to provide answers to the following questions:

- How was the Naira Redesign implemented in 2022?
- What were the causes or reasons for Naira Redesign?
- How did the Naira Redesign impact small-scale businesses in Bosso Local Government Area of Niger State?

Aim of the Paper

This paper primarily examines the Impact of Naira Redesign on Small Scale Businesses in Bosso Local Government Area..The Objectives of the study are:

- To document the implementation of Naira Redesign 2022.
- To highlight the causes or reasons for Naira Redesign.
- To analyse the impact of Naira Redesign on Small Scale Businesses in Bosso Local Government Area.

Implementation of Naira Redesign

The implementation of the 2022 Naira Redesign was carried out in phases. In October 2022, Mr Godwin Emefiele, then Governor of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) announced a major currency redesign initiative, beginning with the ₦200, ₦500 and ₦1000 denominations starting from December 15, 2022 with the old denomination ceasing to be legal tender after January 3 2022,. 2023. According to him, it is considered best practice for central banks to redesign and circulate new currency every five to eight years.¹² It is on record that the last time the CBN had the Naira redesigned was in 2014 when only ₦100 note were redesigned to commemorate Nigeria's centenary. By the provisions of Sections 2(b), 18(a) and 19(a) and (b) of the CBN Act 2007, the apex bank sought and received the approval of the then President, Muhammadu Buhari, to redesign, produce, release, and circulate a new series of the Naira notes at all levels.¹³ The approval was granted by the President, and the new currency began circulating on December 15, 2022.¹⁴

¹⁰ National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) "National Employment Report: Unemployment and Underemployment Report Q4 2019". (2020), Accessed at <https://nigerianstat.gov.ng/download/1025>. Retrieved on 9 July 2025.

¹¹ Nigerian Bureau of Statistics (NBS) "Employment Statistics in Nigeria."(2022) Accessed at <https://www.nigerianstat.gov.ng>. Retrieved on 9 July 2025.

¹² The Central Bank of Nigeria. Redesigning of the Currency". www.cbn.gov.ng (2022). Accessed May 14th from www.cbn.gov.ng>.out CSD > Retrieved on 27 march 2025.

¹³ CBN "Central bank of Nigeria Act" Accessed May 14th from www.cbn.gov.ng>.out CSD > (2007) Retrieved on 27 march 2025.

¹⁴ Mahammed, O. "Naira Redesign and its aftermath affect free trade in Nigeria" Accessed June 3 from [Bussinessday.ng](https://www.bussinessday.ng) / opinion / article / how-Naira-redesign-and-itsaftermath-affect-free-trade-in-Nigeria/ Retrieved on 17 April 2025.

According to CBN, the redesigned and old denomination notes shall remain legal tender and circulate together until January 31st, 2023,¹⁵ after which the old currencies cease to be legal. Tender. That was the initial deadline given by the CBN to end the circulation of these Naira notes. However, the replacement process of the old currency was marred by administrative glitches, un-cooperative behavior by bank customers and the CBN directive that the redesigned notes would only be dispensed through Automated Teller Machines (ATMs) with a withdrawal limit of ₦20,000 per day. The senior staff of the apex bank were asked to visit remote areas to weigh the level of awareness and compliance to the new policy. The feedback they received was negative and the initial deadline was around the corner. Then, it became clear that there was a problem on the ground because the demand for the new currency outweighed its availability as predicted by the Scarcity Theory. This led some people to take advantage of the situation exchanging old notes for new ones for a huge premium.

On January 30, 2023, a day before the initial deadline,¹⁶ the Governor of the Central Bank of Nigeria announced that on the president's orders the deadline would be extended by ten days. But the situation worsened and became unbearable leading to violent protests by youths, small and medium enterprises owners, petty traders, and depositors. This resulted in the vandalization of many banks, especially those in the urban areas as people struggled to access cash for their daily needs. This severely disrupted economic activities in the country.

Anoke and Okpanaki highlighted that small and medium enterprises (SMEs) owners were the hardest hit because they rely heavily on cash for carrying out their economic transactions.¹⁷ Electronic transfers and point of sale (POS) transactions often face technical issues, further complicating their ability to conduct business. By the end of February 2023, the CBN confirmed that the old Naira notes were no longer legal tenders. Though the then President Muhammadu Buhari approved the decision, several state governors objected. The governors from Kaduna, Kogi, Zamfara, and Ogun filed a lawsuit against the federal government and successfully challenged the implementation of the currency redesign policy.¹⁸ The Naira redesign policy revealed weaknesses in Nigeria's economy. The CBN reluctantly complied with the Supreme Court judgment, reintroducing the old ₦200, ₦500, and ₦1000 notes into circulation. However, the damage had already been done. Nigeria's nominal GDP loss for the first quarter was estimated at ₦10 trillion due to chaos caused by the Naira redesign policy and many informal businesses suffered losses as they had to pay higher premiums to access physical cash.¹⁹

The Naira Redesign of 2022 in Nigeria implemented by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), aimed at curbing inflation, controlling the money in circulation and reducing illicit financial flows.

Breakdown of the Implementation of Naira Redesign of 2022:

- *Redesign of Naira Notes:* The CBN redesigned the N200, N500, and N1000 banknotes and they were introduced into circulation from December 15, 2022.²⁰

¹⁵ Pillah, T. P. "currency Redesign and Monetary Policy of Nigeria: An Evaluation" *International Journal of Public Administration and Management Research (IJPAMR)*, 8 (4), (2022), 46-53

¹⁶ Pillah, T. P. "Currency Redesign and Monetary Policy of Nigeria: An Evaluation" *International Journal of Public Administration and Management Research (IJPAMR)*, 8 (4), (2022), 46-53

¹⁷ Anoke, A.F and Okpanaki, I. "Microfinance financial strategies and business growth of women entrepreneurs in Gboko, Benue State Nigeria." *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 22(5), (2022), 69-80

¹⁸ Oyadeyi, O. "The Proposed Naira Redesign, the Ensuing Cash Crunch, and Their Implications on the Nigerian Economy" Evidence from Q1 2023. Munich Personal RePEc Archive, 1-1.

¹⁹ Ibid.

²⁰ The Central Bank of Nigeria. "Redesigning of the Currency". www.chb.gov.ng (2022). Accessed May 14th from www.chb.gov.ng > out>CSD > Retrieved on 27 March 2025.

- *Cash Withdrawal Limits:* The CBN set a maximum cash withdrawal limit of N100, 000 for individuals and N500, 000 for corporate entities per week..Later on, the limits were revised to N500, 000 for individuals and N5, 000,000 for corporate entities.²¹
 - *Cash Swap Program:* The CBN introduced a cash swap program in rural and underserved areas, allowing individuals to exchange old Naira notes for new ones through super agents and Deposit Money Banks (DMBs).²²
 - *Deposit Deadline:* The CBN set a deadline of January 31, 2023, for the old Naira notes to be deposited, after which they would cease to be legal tender.²³
 - *Challenges and Controversies:* The implementation faced several challenges, including long queues, riots, and criminal destruction of bank properties.²⁴
- Many Nigerian's plight were worsened as they struggled with restricted access to the new notes coupled with the withdrawal of the old banknotes, leading to distressing scenes including instances of individuals collapsing and losing their lives while queuing at banks for cash. Some state governors as earlier mentioned also instituted a legal action against the CBN, challenging the legitimacy of the cash redesign policy.
- *Revised Deadline:* Following the controversies, the Nigerian President ordered the old N200 notes to be brought back into circulation, while the N500 and N1000 notes ceased to be legal tender. The Supreme Court later ruled that the old Naira notes remain valid till December 31, 2023.²⁵ The Naira Redesign was implemented for various reasons which would be discussed in the succeeding section.

Causes or Reasons for Naira Redesign

Questions arise about the necessity of Currency Redesign and withdrawal restrictions, especially in a country seeking to liberalize its financial sector. However, the CBN cited several reasons for the redesign including controlling the money supply and promoting the E-Naira. By requiring individuals to deposit old notes to access new ones, the redesign aims to reduce the money in circulation which could help lower prices. The policy encouraged a shift towards a cashless system and greater use of E-Naira. According to Mr., Emefiele, over 85% of Naira was outside the banking system, which hindered the CBN's ability to manage inflation effectively..²⁶ Some of the causes or reasons for Naira Redesign are highlighted hereunder:

Combating counterfeiting

The CBN noted that Nigeria had not redesigned its currency for over 20 years, making it vulnerable to different shades of counterfeiting... According to the governor, recent developments in imaging technology and printing press(s) have made counterfeiting far easier.²⁷ The CBN recently reported an increase in the number of counterfeit transactions especially in higher denominations such as N500 and N1000. According to Vanguard,²⁸

²¹ Central Bank of Nigeria "Redesigning of the Currency".

²² CBN "Issuance of New Naira Banknotes." Press Remarks by Godwin Emefiele, October 26, 2023, Accessed at <http://www.cbn.nig/en/> Retrieved on April 14 2025.

²³ CBN "Issuance of New Naira Banknotes." Press Remarks by Godwin Emefiele, October 26, 2023, Accessed at <http://www.cbn.nig/en/> Retrieved on April 14 2025.

²⁴ Central Bank of Nigeria "On Progress of Implementation of New Redesigned Currency by the Central Bank of Nigeria" Press Statement by Godwin Emefiele, Jan 29, 2023, Accessed at <http://www.cbn.nig/en/> Retrieved on April 15, 2025.

²⁵ Central Bank of Nigeria "On Progress of Implementation of New Redesigned Currency by the Central Bank of Nigeria" Press Statement by Godwin Emefiele, Jan 29, 2023, Accessed at <http://www.cbn.nig/en/> Retrieved on April 14 2025.

²⁶ Emefiele, G, "Press remarks on issuance of new Naira banknotes" by Godwin I. Emefiele, Governor, Central Bank of Nigeria. Accessed at (www.cbn.gov.ng/out/2022/ced/press%20remarks%20on%20new%20banknotesoct2022%20final.pdf), 26 October 2022 Retrieved on 22 March, 2025.

²⁷ CBN "The Rate of Counterfeiting Is Less than One Per Cent" Press Release, 2016.

²⁸ The Vanguard Newspaper "The History of currency introduction and redesign in Nigeria" Accessed at [https://guardian.ng/opinion/the-history-of-currency-introduction-and-redesigninnigeria/\(2022\)](https://guardian.ng/opinion/the-history-of-currency-introduction-and-redesigninnigeria/(2022)). Retrieved on 9 July 2025.

the activities of currency accumulators have become apparent as very dirty, smelly Naira notes have been in circulation, particularly since political events increased across the country, which is a sign that such notes essentially been stockpiled in moist places and for a long period of time hence the need for a redesign to curtail the situation.

Reduction of Cash Insecurity and Money Laundering

The redesign also aimed at reducing cash insecurity and money laundering. The CBN believed that the new policy would encourage a cashless society, deterring criminals such as extortionists and kidnappers, by making ransom payments more difficult. While the policy aimed to curb criminal activities such as kidnapping and money laundering, it also created significant challenges for SME's, particularly those reliant on cash transactions. It is certainly true that some members of the public simply walk away with huge sums of hard-earned money that cannot be deposited in banks or invested for fear of being apprehended by the authorities. With the introduction of the new Naira, these speculators will suffer losses as their holdings will be worthless in due course as they will not be able to transfer money to bank but then, as much as the redesign would have probably curbed the kidnapping rate, how about the dearth of Naira it caused for all Nigerians especially Small Scale Enterprisers?

Reduction of Money Influence on Electoral Processes

The CBN also cited reducing the influence of money on Nigeria's electoral process as a reason for the redesign. This included discouraging vote-buying and the use of money to influence elections. This was contrary to the viral propaganda that the policy targeted at a presidential candidate of a particular party because the redesigning of the Naira happened at a time (which could have happened coincidentally) Nigerians were preparing for their general elections.²⁹

In a bit to address counterfeiting, inflation and financial security, the Naira Redesign plan was hatched. But the sudden shift to a cashless economy paired with difficulties in accessing new notes, led to considerable disruptions for Small Scale Businesses especially those dependent on cash inclined transactions. On this note, the impacts of Naira Redesign on Small Scale Businesses in Bosso LGA would be examined thereafter.

Impact of Naira Redesign on Small Scale Businesses in Bosso

The study examines the Impact of Naira Redesign on Small Scale Businesses in Bosso judging from oral accounts. Oral interviews with Small Scale Enterprisers provides the basis for the examination of the impacts of Naira Redesign on these businesses. In Bosso LGA, the impacts were majorly negative ranging from economic, social, technological and psychological impact, with 90% of respondents reporting adverse effects on their businesses. However, a small minority indicated they found opportunity amidst the challenges, citing positive benefits such as increased demand for digital payment systems and the rise of new business models and ventures.

Based on oral testimonies the major economic impact of Naira Redesign on Small Scale Businesses in Bosso LGA was the Disruption of Business Transactions. Interviews highlighted the policy's detrimental impact, notably the disruption of business transactions. The redesign of naira made it more difficult for retailers to collect payments and generated confusion, particularly among those who were not familiar with the new approach. Trader Friday asserts that the non-acceptability of the new naira note brought about stagnation in his business transactions, incurred extra cost for goods and services as well as led to low sales and severe extortion

²⁹ Taylor, J. B. "Improvements in monetary policy and implications for Nigeria. Keynote Address Money Market Association of Nigeria". Abuja, (2004), pg 5-6.

from POS operators.³⁰ In the same vein, Ephraim and Ejodamen revealed that the naira redesign policy drastically reduced the number of banknotes in circulation and induced widespread economic turmoil this is because many of the rural population rely on cash transactions and do not have bank accounts into which they could deposit old notes or convert to new currency ahead of the deadline, let alone use online payment services for transactions to bypass resulting currency shortages and wealth inequality.³¹

Another incisive economic effect of Naira Redesign on the SSE's of Bosso LGA was The Disruption of Supply Chains.. Bosso is a known hub of small scale enterprises which consist of markets. A popular market in Bosso LGA is named after the town: Bosso-Bosso Market. A significant number of respondents from Bosso Market testified that Naira Redesign hampered the delivery of their farm produce to the market thereby affecting their sales negatively. Chukwudi recounted that he sold his goods too cheaply to raise cash for buying farm produce from farmers, who preferred cash payments due to lack of bank accounts³². The cash scarcity caused by the Naira redesign policy disrupted supply chains, leading to delayed deliveries and customer dissatisfaction.

Socially, Naira Redesign caused Untold Hardship for the Small Scale Enterprisers. Many respondents commented that Naira Redesign was displeasing, stressful, demoralising and terrible. Mahmud remarked that food hike, hunger and anger became the order of the day.³³ Increased Stress and Time Wastage was another social effect of Naira Redesign on SSE's of Bosso LGA. Quite a significant number of the SSE owners in Bosso interviewed certified that Naira Redesign caused delay and wastage of their precious business time because of long queues at banks. Adamu reported that excessive time spent in banks wasted precious time and hurt their business, taking away from time that could be spent at their business center.³⁴ Jacob further reiterated that time wasted at the banks detracted him from his business productive.³⁵ Naira Redesign affected the standard of living and feeding pattern of most homes of Small Scale Enterprises in Bosso LGA. All the interviewees from Bosso LGA attested to the fact that Naira Redesign interrupted their feeding patterns. Oral Sources confirmed that they cut back on spending, chose budget-friendly food options, and encouraged their children to be understanding and flexible.³⁶ Movement patterns were also affected. In tandem with the statement, Adiodun corroborated that Naira Redesign period was a peculiar time where everywhere felt lifeless, and many were confined to their homes due to the limitations on transactions and borrowing. The lack of access to cash and transportation issues kept everyone at home, and social gatherings were put on hold.³⁷

In the Technological lens, Naira Redesign caused an over dependency on Technology which many times may fail and cannot always be relied on, increased Cyber Crimes, limited Cash Inflow and Outflow, network issues, time wasting for transactions to be processed, decreased Standard of Living and Low Disposable Income. This is in line with Hornborgs view "there may be a temporary cash shortage during the redesigning process, which could result in a cash shortage and financial and technological system disruptions."³⁸ Cyber security Risk were also heightened during the period. A great percentage of the interviewees agreed that they experienced losses in their businesses due to fake online transactions all in a bid to make little profit at the time. Most of the SSE's

³⁰ Mr Okezie Friday Mpama, Age 40, Male, Trader, Interviewed in Bosso LGA Minna, 25th March 2025.

³¹ Ephraim B. Ogoegbulem, O. & Ejodamen, P. "The Nigerian eNaira and the currency redesign policy: a review on their effectiveness" *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Publications (IJMRAP)*5(12) (2023), 31-345(12) Accessed at (<https://ijmr.com/wpcontent/uploads/2023/05/IJMRAP-V5N11P115Y23.pdf>)

³² Mr Chukwudi, Age 30, Male, Market Trader, Interviewed in Bosso LGA, 20th April 2025..

³³ Mahmud.. Lapai, Age 35, Male, Teacher and Shop Owner, Interviewed in Bosso LGA Minna, 25th April 2025.

³⁴ Adamu Moh'd, Age 39, Male, Computer business centre owner, Interviewed in Bosso LGA Minna, 26th April 2025.

³⁵ Jacob Omaba, Age 28, Male Chemist, Interviewed in Bosso LGA Minna, 27th April 2025.

³⁶ Mrs. Esther Gold, Age 50, Female, Worker, Interviewed in Bosso LGA Minna, 24th April 2025.

³⁷ Mr. Ogunleye Abiodun, Age 50, Male, Teacher, Interviewed in Bosso LGA Minna, 24th April 2025.

³⁸ Hornborg, A. "How to turn an ocean liner: a proposal for voluntary degrowth by redesigning money for sustainability, justice, and resilience." *Journal of Political Ecology*, 24(1), (2017), 623632.

were vulnerable to cyber security risks, such as hacking and data breaches, when adopting digital payment platforms and fintech solutions. Caroline recounted that she encountered having disputes with many customers, getting scammed, and facing issues with reversed transactions after customers had already left.³⁹

Furthermore, the psychological health of SSE owners in Bosso was affected. Naira Redesign took a toll on the mental health of these Enterprisers. Depression, Frustration, Anxiety and Hopelessness and Depression were evident during the period. Adamu expressed his unhappiness, stating that his earnings were insufficient to support his family leading to frustration.⁴⁰ Okezie affirms the struggle to locate a cash source caused significant mental strain, impacting his well-being.⁴¹ In Bosso, Naira Redesign policy greatly impacted negatively the flow of business of most small businesses thereby hampering its economic progress and social development at the period.

Conclusions and Recommendations

This paper has analysed the impact of Naira Redesign on Small Scale Businesses with on Bosso LGA. Despite the CBN's 2022 Naira redesign program's alleged advantages, it has had disastrous impacts on Nigerians, especially small scale business owners and rural residents who found it extremely difficult to conduct their businesses during the period. The scarcity of naira caused by redesign of naira, which made government withdraw the old naira notes, left enterprises to no other choice than buying naira from point of sales (POS) operators with high charges. The naira money was used in buying naira in Nigeria, which seriously brought a halt in most businesses in Bosso LGA.

Consequent upon to the above analysis, the study provides the following recommendations for future policy implementations in Nigeria:

1. The Government in collaboration with the CBN should apply a phased approach that allows both old and new currencies to coexist while gradually transitioning to a cashless system.
2. Increased Communication, Publicity and Awareness Programme aimed at increasing access to banking services for unbanked populations should be embarked upon by the Government to increase awareness of the new currency.
3. The Government should prioritise investment in digital infrastructure and provision of adequate training for Small Scale Businesses to facilitate the adoption of electronic payment systems and reduce reliance on cash transactions.

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³⁹ Mrs. Omoyemi Caroline, Age 49, Female, Business Owner, Interviewed in Bosso LGA Minna, 26th April 2025.

⁴⁰ Mr. Okezie Friday, Age 40, Male, Public Servant and Trader, Interviewed in Bosso LGA Minna, 26th April 2025.

⁴¹ Mr. Adamu Mohammed, Age 39, Male, Civil Servant, Interviewed in Bosso LGA Minna, 25th April 2025

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